

Some Coumarins from Malon-2,5-xylicidic Acid and Substituted Salicylaldehydes

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Malon-2,5-xylicidic acid has been condensed with 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5-nitro-, 3,5-dichloro-, 3,5-dibromo-, 3,5-dinitro-, 3,5-di-iodo-, and 3-chloro-5-nitro-salicylaldehydes in presence of various condensing agents. The corresponding coumarins have been prepared for the first time. During these condensations several Schiff's bases are formed by hydrolysis of the acid and subsequent reaction of the released amine with the aldehyde. These Schiff's bases also have been isolated and identified. In all these condensations a trace of pyridine has been found to be the best catalyst.

The preparation of malon-2,5-xylicidic acid and some of its derivatives has already been described¹. The formation of coumarin-3-carboxy-2',5'-xylicidide has also been mentioned. This communication deals with the synthesis of some substituted coumarins (I) by the condensation of the acid with 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5-nitro-, 5-chloro-3-nitro-, 3,5-dichloro-, 3,5-dibromo-, 3,5-di-iodo-, and 3,5-dinitro-salicylaldehydes. All these aldehydes were prepared by well-known methods recorded in literature. The condensations were carried out either in absence of any condensing agent or in presence of a trace of pyridine, piperidine, or glacial acetic acid. Pyridine in traces was found to be the most effective catalyst.

The usual procedure involves heating the aldehyde and the acid in equimolecular proportion on a steam bath for 4 hr. In experiments where the condensing agent is used, a drop of the agent is added to the above mixture. The mass first melts to a clear mobile liquid and this in course of time sets to a solid. On extraction the product is found invariably to be a mixture of the coumarin (I) and the Schiff's base (II). In no case product (III) was isolated.

Formation of the Schiff's base is a common feature in all these condensations. A portion of malon-2, 5-xylic acid hydrolyses in the course of the reaction and the amine, thus released, condenses with the aldehyde. This occurs only in the condensation of salicylaldehyde and its derivatives and has not been observed in the case of aromatic aldehydes which do not have a hydroxyl group *ortho* to the aldehyde group. The exact reason for this behaviour is not clear and this phenomenon is under investigation.

The coumarin derivatives are generally yellow or orange in colour and their yields range from 25 to 60%. The Schiff's bases are orange to scarlet-red in colour and their yields range from 25 to 40%. Separation of the coumarin from the Schiff's base could easily be made by fractional crystallisation from ethanol in which the former is very sparingly soluble. The identity of each Schiff's base was further confirmed by synthesising it from malon-2,5-xylic acid and the appropriate aldehyde.

Preliminary experiments in the preparation of cobalt complexes with the Schiff's bases were also carried out with encouraging results. These will be reported later.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of 5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde with Malon-2,5-xylic Acid.—A mixture of the acid (1 g.), the aldehyde (0.6 g.) and a drop of pyridine was heated on a steam bath for 4 hr. The mixture first melted to a clear yellow liquid and then set to a solid yellow mass within an hour. The contents were then cooled and digested with a saturated solution of sodium carbonate (10 ml). The alkali extract was decanted and the residue washed well with water. The alkali extract on being acidified with HCl (conc.) did not form any precipitate. The residue was boiled with ethanol (15 ml) and filtered. The ethanolic extract on cooling deposited bright yellow needles of 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzylidene-2',5'-xylicidene, m. p. 85°. (Found: Cl, 13.60. $C_{15}H_{14}ONCl$ requires Cl, 13.68%). The product developed a violet colour with ferric chloride. The identity was further confirmed by synthesising an authentic specimen by condensing 2,5-xylicidene and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde.

The residue, left after boiling with ethanol, was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. Yellow needle-shaped crystals of 6-chlorocoumarin-3-carboxy-2',5'-xylicidide, m. p. 212°, were obtained. (Found: Cl, 10.55. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3NCl$ requires Cl, 10.84%).

The other aldehydes were also condensed with malon-2,5-xylicidic acid in the same manner and the products extracted as described above. The results obtained are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Coumarin derivatives.

No.	Name.	Formula.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1	6-Chloro-R	$C_{18}H_{14}O_3NCl$	212°	Cl : 10.55%	10.84%
2	6-Bromo-R	$C_{18}H_{14}O_3NBr$	215°	Br : 21.30	21.51
3	6-Nitro-R	$C_{18}H_{14}O_5N_2$	173°	N : 8.27	8.30
4	6,8-Dichloro-R	$C_{18}H_{13}O_3NCl_2$	162°	Cl : 19.47	19.62
5	6,8-Dibromo-R	$C_{18}H_{13}O_3NBr_2$	160°	Br : 35.26	35.47
6	6,8-Di-iodo-R	$C_{18}H_{13}O_3NI_2$	150°	I : 46.40	46.60
7	6,8-Dinitro-R	$C_{18}H_{13}O_7N_3$	190°	N : 10.80	10.96
8	6-Chloro-8-nitro-R	$C_{18}H_{13}O_5N_2Cl$	155°	Cl : 9.49	9.53

R stands for coumarin-3-carboxy-2',5'-xylicidide.

TABLE II

Schiff's bases.

No.	Name.	Formula.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ONCl	85°	Cl : 13.60%	13.68%
2	2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ONBr	68°	Br : 26.29	26.31
3	2-Hydroxy-5-nitro-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂	184°	N : 9.28	9.30
4	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichloro-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ONCl ₂	110°	Cl : 24.32	24.35
5	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dibromo-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ONBr ₂	150°	Br : 41.55	41.78
6	2-Hydroxy-3,5-di-iodo-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ONI ₂	165°	I : 53.12	53.25
7	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dinitro-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₃	212°	N : 12.01	12.10
8	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-3-nitro-R	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	190°	Cl : 10.50	10.55

-R stands for -benzylidene-2',5'-xylidine.

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